

Kinetic Study of Nickel Exchange on Na-, Ca- and Mg-Illites

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The kinetics of Ni²⁺ ion exchange on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites has been studied at four temperatures 16, 26, 36 and 46°. The mechanism of exchange is film diffusion as indicated by application of interruption and equation (ϕ) tests. Kinetic parameters, diffusion coefficients, half time of exchange, energies of activation have also been calculated at all the four temperatures and were used to predict the theoretical behaviour of Ni²⁺ exchange on the illite surface.

THE ion exchange reaction in clays and soils has proved to be of fundamental importance in agriculture and technology. Since the ion exchange reaction involves transport of ions, it is heterogeneous and cannot be dealt with by simple kinetic rate laws. Quite a bit of basic research has been reported on the kinetics of exchange reactions. Most of the investigations are based upon the pioneering work of Boyd *et al*¹ on organic zeolites. Substantial work has dealt with synthetic ion exchangers²⁻⁴. Information regarding kinetics of exchange on soils and clays is meagre^{5,6}.

Nickel is an important trace element in plant nutrition and its formulations as NiCl₂ are often used as fungicide in soils. Illite is an important clay mineral occurring in argillaceous sediments found on a large scale in India and other parts of world. The mineral has been found to possess reactive sites at the edges, corners, interlayer and interlattice positions^{7,8}. Despite considerable amount of work, very little attention has been paid to the kinetic aspect of the problem of exchange of Ni(II). The present work attempts to obtain information on the kinetics of exchange of Ni(II) on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites.

Experimental

Materials and Methods: Illite used in these studies was from Morris, Illinois. Less than 2 μ m clay fraction was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation. It was converted into chloride free Na-illite and then into Ca- and Mg-saturated illites by ion exchange technique⁹. The concentration of the mineral suspensions ranged from 11.6 to 13.2 gl⁻¹. The base exchange capacity (BEC) of the Na-illite was 235 μ eq/g clay, determined by the method of Ganguli¹⁰. For the determination of the BEC of Ca- and Mg-illite, a known volume of suspension was treated with a mixture consisting of 1M NiCl₂ in 0.001M HCl (keeping in contact for 24 hrs) and the amount of calcium and magnesium released was estimated, giving the value of 205 and 220 μ eq/g clay respectively.

The ion exchange reaction between Na-, Ca- and Mg-saturated illites and Ni²⁺ can be represented as :

(where M = Ca²⁺ or Mg²⁺).

The ion exchange reaction on clay could be either particle or film or mixed particle diffusion controlled reaction. The rate determining step of above exchanges was determined by (i) interruption¹¹ and (ii) equation tests¹².

The interruption test was carried out at four temperatures viz. 16, 26, 36, 46° at two concentrations of Ni(II) by withdrawing Ni(II) solution from Na-, Ca- and Mg-illite particles for a brief interval of time (5 min) and then adding the solution again. This was done at two time intervals i.e., after 10 and 30 min in two set of experiments. The concentration of Ni²⁺ at different time intervals was estimated before and after interruption. The results are given in Fig. 1.

For kinetic study, 10 ml of appropriate clay suspensions were treated with 15 ml of standard Ni(II) (N/100) solution. The solutions were kept in contact for appropriate time intervals (2-60 min). The contents were centrifuged and the concentration change in the suspensions was determined using EDTA titration in the case of Ni²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions and flame photometry in case of Na⁺. It gives the uptake of Ni²⁺ as a function of time. The values of fractional attainment of equilibrium (F) (F = amount of Ni²⁺ exchange at time t / amount exchanged at equilibrium) were calculated at 16, 26, 36 and 46°.

The value of the function ϕ may be calculated to decide the rate controlling process. The value of ϕ is given by the following relation :

$$\phi = \frac{X\bar{D}_s}{CDr_0} (5 + 2\alpha_B^A) \quad \dots (3)$$

where X = concentration of fixed ionic groups taken

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Fig. 1. Plot of fractional attainment of equilibrium (F) vs time (t) for Ni²⁺ exchange on Na- (●, ×, ○, ▲), Ca- (Δ, *, -●-, -○-) and Mg- (-○-, ■, ⊙, □) illites at 16, 26, 36 and 46° respectively. Dotted line (···) indicates interruption for 10 min and solid line (—) for 30 minutes.

Fig. 2. Plot of Bt vs t for Ni²⁺ exchange on Na- (●, ×, ○, ▲), Ca- (Δ, *, ■, □) and Mg- (⊙, □, -●-, -○-) illites at 16, 26, 36 and 46° respectively.

as equivalent to maximum adsorption, C=concentration of counter ion in solution (meq cm⁻³), \bar{D} =interdiffusion coefficient in the ion exchanger, D=interdiffusion coefficient in the film, r₀=radius of illite particle (10⁻⁴ cm), δ=film thickness (10⁻² cm in unstirred solution) and α_B^A the separation factor.

The separation factor α_B^A was calculated from the equivalent ionic fractions using the equation :

$$\alpha_{M^{2+}}^{Ni^{2+}} = \frac{\bar{X}_{Ni} \cdot X_M}{X_M \cdot X_{Ni}} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\alpha_{Na^+}^{Ni^{2+}} = \frac{\bar{X}_{Ni} \cdot (X_{Na})^2}{(\bar{X}_{Na})^2 \cdot X_{Ni}} \quad \dots (5)$$

where \bar{X} =equivalent ionic fraction in clay phase and X=mole fraction in solution phase.

The values of \bar{D} (effective diffusion coefficient in the illite phase) were calculated from the relationship : $\bar{D} = Br_0^2/\pi^2$. The value of B was obtained from the plots of Bt vs t (Fig. 2), the Bt values have been obtained from the suitable values of F as tabulated by Reichenberg¹⁵. With the help of Wheelers¹⁴ relationship the values of D (effective diffusion coefficient in the film) were calculated as : $\bar{D} = \frac{D\epsilon}{2}$, where ε is the pore volume of illite.

The fractional pore volume of Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites were determined from bulk and particle densities.

Results and Discussion

The rate determining step in ion-exchange process is interdiffusion of the exchanging counter

ions either within the ion exchanger itself or in an adherent liquid film¹. Interruption test showed no change in the rate of exchange. No concentration gradient was found to exist in the clay and the rate depended on the concentration difference across the film. Thus, the rate determining step in the Ni²⁺ exchange on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites at all experimental temperatures was governed by film diffusion.

The values of φ calculated for Ni²⁺ exchange on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites showed that the values of φ were greater than unity and were in the order Na->Ca->Mg-illites (vide Table 1), indicating that the rate is controlled by film diffusion (φ>>1) and the order of exchange being Na->Ca->Mg-illites.

A plot of F vs t (Fig. 3) showed that the Ni²⁺ exchange on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites was characterized by a rapid initial exchange followed by subsequent falling in the rate as the concentration gradient diminished in the film. With rise in temperature from 16 to 46° the rate of exchange in all the cases also increased. This might be due to an increase in the mobility of Ni²⁺ with increase in temperature. The half time of exchange was calculated from the expression :

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.23 \frac{\delta r_0 X}{DC} \quad \dots (6)$$

The values of t_{1/2} obtained are recorded in Table 1, the t_{1/2} values are in the order Mg>Ca>Na. The half time of exchange (t_{1/2}) decreased with increase in time of contact i.e., the rates of exchange as characterized by half times increased with time of contact. With rise in temperature the t_{1/2} values

decreased confirming the earlier inference that rate of exchange increased with rise in temperature and the order of rate exchange is Na->Ca->Mg-illites.

An examination of Table 1 revealed that the rate of diffusion in the aqueous phase was much faster than in the illite phase in all the exchanges at all the four experimental temperatures and the order was Na->Ca->Mg-illites. The diffusion coefficients increased with rise in temperature as well as with passage of time i.e., the rate of exchange of Ni²⁺ ion on Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites increased with time and temperature.

(Table 1 Contd.)

TABLE 1—DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS AND ϕ VALUES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND TIMES FOR Ni²⁺ EXCHANGE ON Na-, Ca- AND Mg-ILLITES

Temperature (K)	Time (min)	(F)	$\bar{D} \times 10^{13}$ (cm ² /sec)	$D \times 10^{13}$ (cm ² /sec)	ϕ	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (hr)
<i>Na-Illite</i>						
289	2	0.108	0.93	0.30	171	42.6
	5	0.216	1.54	0.50	156	28.9
	10	0.487	4.78	1.54	214	14.4
	15	0.649	6.39	2.06	231	8.7
	22	0.812	9.04	2.92	262	6.3
299	30	0.921	11.39	3.67	281	4.4
	2	0.114	1.01	0.33	162	40.1
	5	0.228	1.74	0.56	180	26.2
	10	0.514	5.46	1.76	192	11.3
	15	0.659	6.91	2.23	212	7.8
309	22	0.827	9.79	3.16	242	5.4
	30	0.941	13.38	4.32	260	3.6
	2	0.121	1.13	0.36	143	38.0
	5	0.242	1.96	0.63	162	24.1
	10	0.545	6.31	2.04	180	10.2
319	15	0.667	7.20	2.32	192	7.0
	22	0.849	10.73	3.46	222	4.8
	30	0.970	16.98	5.48	238	3.0
	2	0.129	1.29	0.42	122	36.1
	5	0.258	2.14	0.69	150	22.2
289	10	0.584	7.44	2.40	171	9.3
	15	0.713	8.62	2.78	182	6.2
	22	0.871	11.92	3.84	206	4.1
	30	1.000	—	—	—	—
	<i>Ca-Illite</i>					
289	2	0.093	0.72	0.24	164	42.9
	5	0.196	1.22	0.40	187	29.1
	10	0.453	4.00	1.31	201	14.5
	15	0.612	5.71	1.87	222	8.9
	22	0.774	7.62	2.50	240	6.5
299	30	0.871	8.74	2.87	269	4.6
	2	0.101	0.82	0.27	151	40.3
	5	0.203	1.36	0.45	171	26.5
	10	0.482	4.69	1.54	182	12.2
	15	0.621	5.91	1.94	206	8.2
309	22	0.792	8.35	2.74	227	5.7
	30	0.900	10.14	3.33	244	4.0
	2	0.111	0.95	0.31	139	39.0
	5	0.222	1.61	0.53	156	25.3
	10	0.520	5.59	1.83	171	11.0
319	15	0.631	6.77	2.22	192	7.9
	22	0.813	9.20	3.02	211	5.3
	30	0.925	11.88	3.89	226	3.6
	2	0.121	1.12	0.37	126	37.3
	5	0.240	1.93	0.63	141	22.6
289	10	0.522	5.61	1.84	169	9.9
	15	0.640	7.33	2.40	174	7.0
	22	0.840	10.49	3.38	200	4.9
	30	0.962	15.64	5.13	211	3.1

<i>Mg-Illite</i>						
289	2	0.083	0.53	0.18	152	43.7
	5	0.167	0.90	0.30	174	29.8
	10	0.442	3.81	1.27	192	15.1
	15	0.582	5.00	1.67	206	9.4
	22	0.750	6.95	2.33	221	6.8
299	30	0.862	8.31	2.78	246	5.0
	2	0.088	0.59	0.20	139	41.2
	5	0.177	1.01	0.34	159	27.6
	10	0.472	4.40	1.47	174	13.9
	15	0.617	5.83	1.94	196	9.1
309	22	0.766	7.41	2.47	213	6.4
	30	0.833	9.24	3.08	233	4.4
	2	0.094	0.68	0.23	130	40.0
	5	0.188	1.02	0.34	148	26.1
	10	0.500	5.09	1.70	162	11.3
319	15	0.625	6.31	2.11	183	8.6
	22	0.781	7.93	2.64	200	6.1
	30	0.906	10.18	3.39	217	4.1
	2	0.100	0.77	0.26	117	38.8
	5	0.200	1.30	0.44	133	24.0
289	10	0.500	5.39	1.80	149	10.6
	15	0.633	6.54	2.18	170	7.8
	22	0.800	8.06	2.87	188	5.3
	30	0.933	12.44	4.15	207	3.5

Fig. 3. Plot of fractional attainment of equilibrium (F) vs time (t) for Ni exchange on Na- (●, ×, ○, ▲), Ca- (△, *, -●-, -○-) and Mg- (○, □, ■, -○-) illites at 16, 26, 36 and 46° respectively.

Since temperature effect has been very useful in providing an insight into the theory of all rate processes, the energetics of Ni²⁺ ion exchange on illite were examined by temperature studies. The diffusion coefficients (D) can be related to temperature by the following expression¹⁵ :

$$D = D_0 e^{-E_a/RT} \quad \dots (7)$$

The activation energy (E_a) was calculated by the linear relationships of log D vs 1/T (Fig. 4) and D₀ by extrapolation. The values are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ENERGY PARAMETERS FOR Ni²⁺ EXCHANGE ON Na-, Ca- AND Mg-ILLITES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (Time 2-30 min.)

Nature of clay	Temperature (K)	E _a (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔH _a (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔS _a (J mole ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG _a (kJ mole ⁻¹)
Na-Illite	289	7.61 to 10.55	5.20 to 8.14	-353.6 to -332.7	101.3 to 104.3
	299		5.12 to 8.06	-353.2 to -331.7	104.3 to 113.7
	309		5.04 to 7.98	-352.4 to -330.0	107.0 to 116.9
	319		4.95 to 7.88	-351.7 to -329.0	109.9 to 120.1
Ca-Illite	289	8.62 to 12.93	6.20 to 10.92	-357.1 to -336.3	103.4 to 114.1
	299		6.12 to 10.84	-356.3 to -335.4	106.4 to 117.4
	309		6.04 to 10.76	-355.3 to -334.3	109.3 to 120.6
	319		5.95 to 10.67	-354.3 to -332.3	111.9 to 123.7
Mg-Illite	289	8.62 to 13.39	6.20 to 11.43	-362.0 to -339.0	104.2 to 116.1
	299		6.12 to 11.35	-361.3 to -338.4	107.3 to 119.4
	309		6.04 to 11.26	-360.4 to -337.9	110.5 to 122.6
	319		5.95 to 11.18	-359.7 to -336.5	113.3 to 125.9

 Fig. 4. Plot of log D vs 1/T for Ni²⁺ exchange on Na-, Ca- (●, ×, ▲, △, □, *) (solid line for Na and dotted line for Ca) and Mg- (—○—, —●—, —○—, +, ●, ■) illites at 2, 5, 10, 15, 22, 30 min interval respectively.

An examination of Table 2 showed that the values of E_a were in the order Mg->Ca->Na-illites and were in the range 7.61 to 13.39 kJ/mole. The magnitude of E_a showed that exchange of Ni²⁺ is a film diffusion controlled process without steric hindrance^{16,17}. The activation energies thus support the deductions drawn above on the interaction of Ni²⁺ with Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites.

The enthalpies of activation (ΔH_a) were calculated from the relationship :

$$\Delta H_a = E_a - RT \quad \dots (8)$$

The values of ΔH_a are given in Table 2. The low values of ΔH_a support the physical type of adsorption involving ion exchange process and the deductions drawn above on the affinity of Ni²⁺ on illites.

The entropy of activation (ΔS_a) was evaluated from the expression¹⁸ :

$$D = 2.72 d \frac{kT}{h} e^{\Delta S_a/R} \quad \dots (9)$$

where d = ionic jump distance, k = Boltzmann constant, h = Planck constant, R = gas constant and T = temperature. The values are recorded in Table 2. The negative values of ΔS_a pointed to a greater order produced during the process of activation. This can be achieved by the formation of activated complex between Ni²⁺ and Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites resulting in a more orderly structure of Ni²⁺ ions on the illite surface due to association or fixation and immobilization of Ni²⁺ with consequent loss in the degrees of freedom of the system during the process¹⁹.

The free energy of activation (ΔG_a) was then determined from the equation,

$$\Delta G_a = \Delta H_a - T\Delta S_a \quad \dots (10)$$

The values are given in Table 2. An examination of the data in Table 2 shows that the values of ΔG_a are positive and are in the order Na->Ca->Mg-illites. The values increased with rise in temperature indicating that the activated complexes of Ni²⁺ with Na-, Ca- and Mg-illites were not very stable and probability of formation of activated complex further decreased with rise in temperature²⁰. The rate of exchange being in order Na->Ca->Mg-illites. The increase in the rate of exchange of Ni²⁺ with rise in temperature was due to large number of ions passing into an activated state with a less stable configuration¹⁹.

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